

A Novel pH Profile in the Reactions of Amines by Chloramine-T

P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and M. D. PRASAD RAO

Department of Chemistry, Berhampur University, Berhampur-760 007 (Orissa)

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The pH profile in the reactions of aniline, *p*-chloro aniline and *m*-chloro aniline with CAT in pure aqueous medium has been reported for the first time. The enhanced reactivity around pH 4.5 has been attributed to the presence of hypochlorous acid as the species. Reactions have been observed to proceed through initial N-Chlorination, which then undergoes rearrangement to give halobenzene till pH 8 and beyond pH 10 hydrolysis and condensation to give azo compounds.

OUR interest in the chlorination of aromatic amines by CAT and NCS was mainly because of measurable rates of chlorination with these reagents. We have recently reported¹ our work on chlorination of aromatic amines by CAT in aqueous acetic acid at varying acidities. We have also recently reported² the oxidation of aromatic amines by CAT in alkaline medium where the products are azobenzenes. The present study involves an investigation of the pH profile of CAT reaction of aniline, *p*-chloro aniline and meta chloro aniline in aqueous system up to pH 6.85 and in aqueous ethanol system at pH 8-12. There is minimal contribution due to solvent effect and there is no perceptible solvent oxidation as well under the conditions.

Second order rate constants have been given in Table 1 for aniline, *p*-chloro aniline and *m*-chloro

TABLE-1

SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR ANILINE, *p*-CHLORO ANILINE AND *m*-CHLORO ANILINE AT VARIOUS pH.

Temp : 35° aqueous medium.

Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹							
	pH→1.6	2.2	4.5	5.4	6.85	8*	10*	12*
Aniline	0.035	0.25	4.1	1.09	0.11	0.006779	0.00595	0.0059
<i>p</i> -chloro aniline	0.041	0.28	4.99	2.22	0.17	0.001951	0.00345	0.0042
<i>m</i> -chloro aniline	0.052	0.25	2.34	1.25	0.167	0.001321	0.00258	0.0025

* All the experiments at pH 8, pH 10 and pH 12 have been done at 60° and in 10% aqueous ethanol (ethanol : water : 10 : 90 V/V) due to solubility consideration. Even then it is clearly seen that the rates are much lower in general.

aniline. It is clear that the pH dependence is not linear in the total pH range, and the rate maximum occurs at pH 4.5. In the first sight it may look as if aniline, *p*-chloro aniline and *m*-chloro aniline having similar H⁺ dependence would have increased

rates of chlorination as competing protonation becomes less. But this would have resulted in a clean steep pH profile. To us it appears that the CAT species is more important and is sensitive to pH. Several species of CAT are current in literature :

(1) CAT(sodium salt) (2) CAT(RNHCl) (3) DCT (4) HOCl (5) H₂O⁺Cl. The hydrolysed species (RNHCl) are important till pH 2.2 and at 6.8 and the near identical rates point to the same type of species. Higuchi³ and Mahadevappa⁴ have obtained evidences for DCT formation in the pH range 4-7 and 3-4 in the CAT-*p*-cresol reaction and in the conductometric measurements respectively. But the best kinetic evidence for DCT formation and chlorination through it would be a second order dependence on CAT, as seen from the equilibrium :

The order with respect to CAT has been checked by varying the concentrations of CAT at pH 4.5. For a three-fold increase in the concentration of CAT the first order rate constant (k_1) almost remained constant indicating the first order dependence on CAT (Table 2). This constancy of the

TABLE-2

VARIATION OF CONCENTRATION OF CAT AT pH 4.5 IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM. [ANILINE]=0.005M, TEMP : 35°

10 ⁴ [CAT]	10 ³ k ₁ sec ⁻¹
4.395	19.19
6.45	19.19
7.97	21.41
8.78	20.51
10.93	21.41

first order rate constants conclusively establishes the first order dependence with respect to CAT. This rules out any DCT formation under our conditions. Hence the only acceptable species in the pH range

